

Connecting the Dots: How Lucid Dreaming and Daily Behavior Interact

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Abstract

The focus of this study is to learn how lucid dreaming can be used to change dream content in a way that is beneficial for the participant. The research delves into the benefits of lucid dreaming, as well as common techniques for lucidity. Furthermore, the study analyzes the positive impact of becoming lucid as a way to treat nightmares. Finally, the researcher shows data that was collected through interviews with research professionals, proving the idea that lucid dreaming can positively change dream content, and discusses instructions for the next steps of lucid dreaming research.

Keywords:

I. Introduction

A trending topic in dream research has to do with lucid dreaming: the idea that a person knows they are aware he is dreaming while in the dream, and can make changes to the content narrative/experience. This process is done during a crucial part of the human cycle, sleep. Sleep, which is often undervalued and frequently sacrificed for productivity and socializing. Getting good sleep is a luxury, but it is also an essential factor in a person's physical and mental wellbeing. About one-third of human life is spent sleeping, and a large chunk of that is dreaming. Providing the human body with sufficient sleep gives a person enough energy to perform daily tasks, maintain a decent mood, have a healthy brain function, and stay in good physical health (National Institute of Neurological Disorders and Stroke).

A lucid dream is when someone is conscious they are in a dream, yet they continue dreaming. It is typical for a person to have a lucid dream multiple times in their lifetime, which is why it is crucial to understand the benefits (Radtke, 2025). Lucid dreaming was first identified in 1913 by a Dutch psychiatrist, Frederik Van Eeden. In his research, he states that while people are sleeping and when they are having lucid dreams, they can know and remember their life as if they are awake (Baird, Mota-Rolim, & Dresler, 2019). However, there was a slight change in his beliefs as the research evolved. Now, dream researchers believe that lucid dreams can be remembered, but not as clearly as a memory someone has during the day. The topic of lucid dreaming gets a little more complicated than simple dreaming; it is harder to understand and to perform. These dreams are similar to thoughts someone can have while they are awake.

The content can be about something that happened during the day or about something completely irrelevant to the individual. Since people spend so much time lucid dreaming in their lives, it is important to understand the effects of lucid dreaming to help create new theories about human life and what causes human actions. As a result of one's control over the mind in a lucid dream, they are able to use that technique to convert bad dreams into something positive and happy.

This research is conducted to understand the benefits of lucid dreaming and see how it affects daily behavior, and act as a possible treatment for nightmares.

II. Methodology

The data collection design and method that is used is a correlational qualitative study done through interviews. It is important to mention that this study is qualitative because the opinions of people and their research are important to collect this data. It is necessary to include different perspectives from qualified professionals to understand why their opinion is what it is and why that opinion should be accepted. This research will also fall under the qualitative section because it's important how people make sense of the relationship between lucid dreams and daily behavior. In an interview, many questions are asked, and active listening is involved, which again falls under the components of a qualitative study. This will also be a correlational study because the data that is being gathered is for the overall purpose of understanding the co-relationship between lucid dreams and human behavior. Correlational studies help prove that one thing is caused by another variable, which is present in this data. In the long run, this research proves that there is a clear relationship between lucid dreams and human behavior. It would be best to use an interview to collect this data because it can leave questions for the interviewee to decide how in-depth they want to go. Additionally, there are open-ended questions, so the interviewer can ask for clarification on anything they need. These were the best methods used to collect data because they allowed for a wide variety of answers and new information to be gathered.

III. Literature Review

3.1 Relevance of Dreams

Neuroscience professionals all around the world study dreaming and its importance for humans. When a person goes to sleep at night, their brain enters different stages of sleep, and based on the stages, it can affect the dreams people get. During these dreams, people might see experiences related to their life, and they can get emotional about it. These emotions can be uplifting and encourage positive dreams, or negative emotions that lead to upsetting dreams. Although people can dream about their life, they may also have dreams completely unrelated to their life. Currently, most dream research discusses the effects that dreams have. However, there is less research on dream content and why people dream what they do. Yet, the minimal research on the study of dreams has taught people that dreaming is beneficial and can soothe highly emotional topics that people have experienced (Walker, 2017).

People are starting to believe that emotions during dreams can affect a person during the day and any possible reactions they have to things. Also, researchers believe that having fears in a dream can make one more fearful during the day or while they are awake. Researchers believe that dreaming can cause a neurobiological function that causes further reactions to the dreams, like a fearful reaction. The same brain circuits that are related to emotions in wakefulness are the same circuits that cause and affect the dreams and emotions a person has while asleep (Sterpenich et al., 2019). Aggressiveness in dreams can result in the same sort of reactions during wakefulness. To put it in simple terms, think about how PTSD and other disorders like depression can affect your sleep, similarly your sleep can also affect your daily behavior.

A common disorder related to dreaming is nightmare disorder. The definition of a nightmare is a vivid experience in a dream that produces lots of anxiety and fear. Nightmares can be classified into two different categories: nightmares and nightmare disorder. Once nightmares start to affect a person, it becomes a disorder (Mayo Clinic, 2021). If a person gets nightmares, it can affect their mood and cause sleep deprivation. Cognitive psychology has shown that dreams can influence emotions and mood even if a person is not aware of that. An example of this is shown through a method called masking. This process is done in a lab where an image is quickly flashed and immediately followed by a second image, blocking the original image. Although someone does not clearly report what the original image was, it can still affect a

person's behavior or emotions. Something similar happens when a person is dreaming. It's easy to think about it as an imprint on a person's brain, specifically, their nervous system, that can have possible effects later (Baird, 2023).

To briefly discuss why people dream what they dream, it is important to know the factors in their life. There are two main components of dream content. The first component is when the dream content is related to events in the person's life. This happens because the experiences of a person during wakefulness are "coded" into their brain, and when a person goes to sleep, the brain gets reactivated. This causes the experiences to show up in dreams, but under different situations. This is why a person can dream about their friend swimming, even if their friend is in no way related to swimming, because the two experiences are brought together in a different situation. The second component of dream content is called activation synthesis. The idea that while in rapid eye movement sleep (REM sleep), the brain gets random activations and links the random activations together to create a story, which is then what a person dreams (Baird, 2023). During these dreams, the hippocampus is highly involved because it is the main part of the brain that deals with memory, imagination, and dreams (Wamsley 2020).

3.2 Neurobiological Basis of Lucid Dreaming

Oftentimes, during a lucid dream, the dream can be very realistic and vivid if in REM sleep, which allows for a wide variety of things to dream about (LaBerge, LaMarca, & Baird, 2018). Originally, lucid dreaming was associated with REM sleep. The authors Baird, Tononi, and LaBerge stated, using electrooculography and pre-agreed eye movements, "lucid dreams could be objectively verified by the presence of distinctive eye movement patterns in the EOG during polysomnographically-verified sleep". Initially, people thought that lucid dreaming only happened during REM sleep, the later stages of the sleep cycle, and was related to times when the central nervous system was highly active (Baird, Tononi, & LaBerge, 2022). However, with new research being conducted, it has been discovered that lucid dreaming also happens during non-REM (NREM) sleep, but it is less common, and the dreams are not as detailed as dreams in REM sleep. A possible reason for the misconception could be that lucid dreams usually happen at the end of a sleep cycle, which also happens to be the time that people are in REM sleep. (Aspy, 2018).

Lucid dreaming is related to physiological activation during REM sleep, including elevated eye movement density. This raises the question of whether lucid dreaming is correlated with or caused by REM sleep. The answer is, it is highly correlated with REM sleep. Research shows that lucid dreams are associated with more than average cortical and subcortical activation during REM sleep. Since the results of previous studies showed that lucid dreams were related to high phasic activation, it proves that they are more common in REM sleep, as there is high phasic activation during REM sleep. Many previous studies believed that lucid dreaming was a different stage than sleep and wakefulness, but newer studies have shown that lucid dreaming does happen during REM sleep, especially during long periods of REM sleep. However, during NREM sleep, the content of the dreams is much different than in REM sleep. For example, there are fewer visuals, and it is more abstract. Also, dreams that happen during NREM sleep are less likely to be remembered because people do not tend to wake up as often during NREM sleep. In both sleep stages, lucid dreaming most often uses the prefrontal cortex of the brain as well as the parietal regions (Baird, Mota-Rolim, & Dresler, 2019).

IV. Methods

There are multiple ways to induce lucid dreams, but the most common is MILD, Mnemonic Induction of Lucid Dreams. This method was created by Dr. Stephen LaBerge and was one of the first reliable ways to induce lucid dreams (LaBerge, LaMarca, & Baird, 2018). Dr. LaBerge attempted to induce lucid dreams so that people could have a prospective memory of what they dreamt. The steps for MILD begin by remembering a past dream and thinking about that dream. Next, one needs to think about an outlier in that dream, a dreamsign. After the patient has done that, they go back to dreaming and

remember this abnormal thing they thought about, and then they start to have lucid dreams. Once MILD was created, it was confirmed to increase lucid dream frequencies, as stated by Dr. LaBerge, “approximately 800% more effective than autosuggestion for inducing signal-verified lucid dreams in the sleep laboratory.” Dr. LaBerge came to a conclusion through his research and found that people tend to get lucid dreams after they do something in the middle of the night, things as reading a book, meditating, or even having intercourse, but these things are so diverse that he thought the conclusion is not these specific things, but what they all have in common; a short period of wakefulness (LaBerge, LaMarca, & Baird, 2018).

The other common inducing technique for lucid dreams is WILD, Wake Initiated Lucid Dreaming (Gish, 2014). In this technique, a participant goes to sleep for a few hours, then wakes up and writes about any dreams he had. Then, he tells himself once he goes back to sleep, he will become lucid, and continue to repeat that phrase a few times. Finally, once the participant goes back to sleep, he will hopefully become lucid.

The last lucid dreaming technique that can be done by oneself is the Wake-Back-To-Bed method. To perform this method, a person has to go to sleep with an alarm set for 4-5 hours after the time they go to bed. Then, they will wake up for a period of time, however long it takes them to gain full consciousness, and then they go back to sleep again. Since the sleep cycles get rearranged, the person has a high possibility of becoming lucid.

All the previous lucid dreaming techniques mentioned can be performed individually at home. However, there are some other methods that can be done in a lab setting. A common technique done at a lab uses an intercom system, which focuses on playing auditory cues. A patient will go to sleep in a room, and beforehand they will have been given instructions by dream scientists on what to do when they hear the auditory cues: wake up but do not move or open eyes. Then, the researchers will ask them questions about any dreams they remember. Afterward, the patient will go back to sleep, and this time, when they have a dream, they will focus on moving their eyes from left to right. If they can successfully do that, it means that they have become lucid in their dream. This signals to the dream scientists that the patient became lucid, and the scientists will be able to track the patient’s brainwaves with an EEG to see what the brain looks like when one becomes lucid. This method is helpful not only for the participant wishing to become lucid, but also for the scientists. Scientists benefit from this by understanding what happens to the brain when a person becomes lucid. This will be helpful for the dream scientists because they will be able to predict for future participants if they are becoming lucid by simply looking at their brain movements while they are asleep.

The next method for lucid dreaming is done with therapists. A participant will meet a sleep therapist, and go over common techniques that the patient can become lucid with, usually WILD and MILD are discussed. Then, the patient tries the technique and reports back to the therapist if it worked or not. Later, the therapist makes a personalized technique for that individual to become lucid. It is unclear how therapists work with their patients to become lucid due to the privacy of the sessions. However, therapists work individually with their patients to create a unique treatment plan, and work to find something that is successful for their patients.

The final noteworthy method for becoming lucid is by using chemicals. There is strong evidence found in research that acetylcholine, a neurotransmitter, is found during REM sleep. A test was done to see if increasing acetylcholine by different doses of donepezil would raise the frequency of lucid dreaming. According to Singh and Gupta, “Nine of the ten participants (90%) reported one or more lucid dreams on the experimental nights on donepezil, with only one participant reporting a lucid dream on a placebo night ($p < 0.01$).” Then, in Singh and Gupta’s 2019 Pre-sleep treatment with galantamine stimulates lucid dreaming: A double-blind, placebo-controlled, crossover study, there were 121 participants

who experienced lucid dreams or had some knowledge about lucid dreaming. The scientist tried to figure out the effects of galantamine, which is an acetylcholinesterase inhibitor. Galantamine has its most effects an hour after it is orally ingested. During the sleep duration of all participants, they had a 30-minute interruption because prior research showed that it increases chances of lucid dreaming (changing the 30 minute interval to longer, like 45 minutes, does not increase the chances of one becoming lucid). In the galantamine test, 62% of participants reported that they had at least one lucid dream; 27% of those participants received a 4 mg dose, and 42% received an 8 mg dose. The research showed that higher doses of galantamine increased the incidence of lucid dreaming, proving that the chemical has a high chance of making someone lucid (LaBerge, LaMarca, & Baird, 2018). The benefits of this chemical were also discussed by Singh and Gupta in their research article, where they stated the same thing as Dr. LaBerge's research, that galantamine is a good way to make someone lucid (Singh and Gupta, 2019).

Once the hard part is done and a person successfully becomes lucid, the next step is for them to change the content of their dream. This is the simple part of lucid dreaming. Once a person is lucid, they will have control over their dream and can make whatever changes they want. They are able to make the changes by thinking about what they want done and performing actions in the dream.

V. Benefits of Lucid Dreaming

Many patients who practice lucid dreaming do so because they dream about traumatic experiences that happened in their lives. About 80% of the human population goes through a traumatic event that can cause PTSD, and about 80% of those people get nightmares (Holzinger, Saletu, & Klösch, 2020). One way that the American Academy of Sleep Medicine tried to prevent nightmares was by lucid dreaming therapy (LDT). LDT has proven to be effective for patients with PTSD and those who have narcolepsy. After patients used the lucid dreaming technique, their nightmares decreased while their sleep quality increased (Holzinger, Saletu, & Klösch, 2020).

As well as being able to cope with things like PTSD, lucid dreaming also has positive effects on the brain and human body. Lucid dreamers often have better attention skills than those who are not able to become lucid. A study was done that included 77 participants with no history of psychiatric or neurological conditions (Loo and Cheng, 2021). Every morning, when a participant woke up from his sleep, he had to write down whether he had a lucid dream or not. He also had to answer a questionnaire stating how often he had dreams and lucid dreams. A testing ANT (attentional network task) was completed by all participants, describing their alertness, orientation, and conflict. The results of the study using ANT and the LuCiD scale (a scale that determines how "present" one was in their dream) showed that lucid dreaming was related to attention tasks and that those who scored high and became lucid could resolve conflicts easily. Additionally, other previous studies have shown that lucid dreamers are very independent, which could be a reason why they can solve conflicts better than those who do not become lucid.

During an interview with Dr. Benjamin Baird, it was understood that having negative emotional content in a dream can have an effect on the person and worsen their mood, and vice versa for positive dream content. Since lucid dreaming gives control of the dream content to the participant, they are usually positive because they can choose what they dream about (Baird, 2023).

In a study done in 2016 by Stumbrys & Erlacher, it was gathered that people who learned to become lucid were able to overcome the fears they faced in their dreams, and it helped their waking mood be more joyful. In a study done by Sikka and Pesonen, they found that a positive dream can lead to a positive mind during the day. Dreams that are very vivid and feel like reality have been shown to be helpful in creating a positive waking mood. To support the previous study, a test

was done to learn more about the relationship between lucidity, dream emotional content, and positive waking mood. For this test, 20 participants were gathered and wore a headband while sleeping and were hooked up to an EEG so their brains could be monitored and evaluated. The EEG mostly looked at REM sleep since it is the common sleep stage where lucidity happens. The results showed that higher levels of lucidity in a patient were correlated with increased positive waking mood (Stocks et al., 2020). Looking at other research articles, more positive benefits of lucid dreaming were discovered. It was realized that lucid dreaming can have positive effects on mental health because people have the power to change their dreams. It can also help with problem-solving, overcoming fears and nightmares, spiritual growth, and emotional, mental, and physical healing.

A few people who have had lucid dreamings were interviewed, and they said that they felt wonderful and empowered after waking up from a lucid dream (Sosnoski, 2023). One of the most important reasons for lucid dreaming was discussed by the American Academy of Sleep Medicine, and they talked about trying to prevent nightmares through lucid dreaming therapy. They believed that lucid dreaming is a recovery of cognitive abilities that are usually related to the reactivation of frontal and front-lateral brain sections, and that this form of therapy allows a patient to alter the contents of their dream, which is especially helpful during a nightmare. According to the American Academy of Sleep Medicine, lucid dreaming is a new and helpful form of therapy because it deals with the problem of nightmares at that instant, rather than other types of therapy. For example, talking to someone about a problem can be helpful, but it doesn't deal with the problem while it is happening (Stocks et al., 2020).

A study was done by researchers that gathered data from participants who tried lucid dreaming to learn about its positive effects. Many people said they liked how they could control their dreams because if they had a nightmare, they could find a solution to it. The researchers also found that some people felt that after learning to become lucid, they slowly started to get fewer nightmares because they could wake themselves up if they wanted to (Mallett et al., 2022).

From reading many research articles, interviewing professionals, and hearing input from people who have become lucid, it is clear that lucid dreaming is worthwhile. It provides power for a person to oversee the content of their dreams and make changes as they wish. This is very helpful because people who get nightmares can use this technique to change a bad dream into something better or wake themselves up if they get too scared. Since it was discovered that lucid dreaming is something good, future health professionals must find a way to incorporate lucid dreaming as a treatment for people who suffer from nightmare disorders, or people who simply want to make changes in the dreams they have. Finally, through primary research (found below), we can safely assume that the benefits of lucid dreaming are indeed real and interesting.

Table 1. Expert Interview Responses on Lucid Dreaming by Theme

Question	Dr. Katja Valli ¹	Dr. Sue Llewellyn ²	Dr. Sofia Tzioridou ³	Robert Hoss ⁴	Dr. Michael Schredl ⁵
What is lucid dreaming?	A dream where you realize that you are dreaming. Some include the requirement of having control over dream features, but that is not necessary.	One where one becomes aware that one is dreaming. It also usually contains bizarre happenings not normal for the person.	In a lucid dream, one is aware that one is dreaming. Thus it is possible to wake up deliberately, to influence the dream actively, or to observe it passively.	The APA defines it as a dream where you know you're dreaming and can influence it. Lucid dreaming typically occurs in REM sleep, where the conscious brain interacts with the unconscious.	In a lucid dream, one is aware that one is dreaming. It is possible to wake up deliberately, to influence the dream actively, or to observe it passively.
What are some techniques for becoming lucid?	Wake Back to Bed (WBTB)—wake early, stay awake ~30 min, return to sleep—is most efficient. Often combined with MILD, where dreamers learn to recognize recurring 'dream signs.'	Various training techniques exist. REM sleep occurs every ~90 minutes, so training to wake at that interval can help induce lucid dreams.	Tholey's Combined Technique, Wake-Initiated Lucid Dreaming (WILD), Wake Back to Bed (WBTB), Reality Testing, and Mnemonic Induction of Lucid Dreams (MILD).	Intention setting, reality testing (e.g., pushing a finger through the hand), MILD, WBTB, WILD (Wake Induced Lucid Dreaming), and various commercial devices.	Reality checks (asking 'Am I dreaming?' several times daily) and Wake Back to Bed (WBTB).

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Question	Dr. Katja Valli ¹	Dr. Sue Llewellyn ²	Dr. Sofia Tzioridou ³	Robert Hoss ⁴	Dr. Michael Schredl ⁵
How are lucid dreams accessed, identified, and assessed?	Healthy participants are woken and asked about their dreams for content analysis or neurophysiologic al analysis (EEG to measure brain activity).	N/A	Researchers invite experienced lucid dreamers. Participants signal lucidity via pre-arranged eye movements (LRLR), monitored with EEG, EOG, and EMG electrodes. Afterward, participants are woken for a dream report.	Clinically, therapists can teach lucid dreaming for therapeutic purposes, such as confronting phobias within the dream using techniques like EFT tapping.	In the lab, lucid dreams are identified by pre-arranged eye-movement patterns (e.g., left-right-left-right), distinguishable from normal REM eye movements.
Do dreams affect daily life, and does daily life affect dreams?	Yes—mood in dreams correlates with next-day mood. Studies show dreaming positively or negatively about a partner shapes next-day interactions. Emotionally loaded memories are more likely to appear in dreams, suggesting a neural pre-selection process.	Clearly lives affect dreams (e.g., PTSD reliving trauma). Highly emotionally arousing dreams can significantly impact the following day's waking consciousness.	The Continuity Hypothesis states dream content reflects the dreamer's current thoughts and concerns. Dreams can also affect daytime mood, problem-solving, and creativity.	The limbic system processes emotional events during sleep and can reduce next-day emotional intensity (e.g., waking up less angry). Dreams draw on analogical reasoning and memory to process emotional situations.	People dream about waking-life topics (e.g., sports, music, gaming). Dreams can affect waking life through mood and creative insight. Strong bidirectional continuity is termed 'second-order continuity.'

Question	Dr. Katja Valli ¹	Dr. Sue Llewellyn ²	Dr. Sofia Tzioridou ³	Robert Hoss ⁴	Dr. Michael Schredl ⁵
What is the relationship between lucid dreams and REM/NREM sleep?	Most lucid dreams occur during REM sleep. Lucid dreaming may involve reactivation of prefrontal brain areas, which are normally suppressed in REM.	Most long, complex dreams occur in REM sleep. NREM dreams exist but are less common; almost no dreaming occurs in slow-wave sleep. The second half of the night is more REM-dominant.	Most lucid dreams occur in REM. Some occur in NREM (particularly N2). No lucid dreams have been recorded in N3 (deep sleep). Claims of lucid awareness during dreamless sleep have not been physiologically verified.	Sleep cycles between deep NREM and REM every ~90 minutes. REM features vivid, interactive storylines. Lucid dreaming mainly occurs in REM, typically toward the end of the night.	Lucid dreams typically occur during REM sleep. Some may occur in NREM—a former PhD student (Tadas Stumbrys) documented a few NREM lucid dreams.
Could lucid dreaming prevent nightmares?	Possibly—3–5% of the population have frequent nightmares. Becoming aware during a nightmare allows the dreamer to alter it, reducing emotional intensity and future recurrence.	Yes, especially for PTSD patients.	Yes, when guided by a certified clinician combined with other techniques. Even the knowledge that lucidity is possible can reduce nightmares through an empowerment effect. Self-guided lucid dreaming for nightmares is not advised.	Yes. Imagery Rehearsal Therapy (IRT) helps patients rewrite nightmare endings. Lucid dreaming can achieve a similar result in real time by confronting fear within the dream.	Yes and no—lucid nightmares are possible. The dreamer must be highly skilled. First-line treatment for nightmares is Imagery Rehearsal Therapy (IRT; Krakow).

Note. Responses have been lightly condensed for clarity. All interviewees are named researchers and practitioners who consented to participation. N/A = interviewee did not address this question.

VI. Rationale

The topic of lucid dreaming is very crucial to dream research because it can be used as a technique to help overcome nightmares. Also, it is important to learn about the ways lucid dreams impact human behavior because sleeping is a large portion of human life and dreams are experienced by a large percentage of the population. So, understanding dreams, specifically lucid dreams, can help provide a clearer understanding of human lives and what might be causing their actions.

VII. Analysis/Results

Results gathered from the five interviews all have in common the concept that lucid dreams are very impactful for humans. This makes sense because all the interviewees had prior knowledge of lucid dreams and had read many articles

and other sources to prove their knowledge. Since they rely on similar studies the information aligns with similar conclusions that lucid dreams impact human behaviour. This accounts for the reason why many of the questions asked had similar responses. The people who were interviewed were all qualified to discuss this topic and their credentials are listed above.

The results prove the research question, “Does lucid dreaming impact the daily behavior of humans?” For example, Dr. Katja Valli gives an example proving her answer to the question. She states that lucid dreams do impact human behavior and when a person dreams about something like their significant other, it may affect the way they view that person the next day. Similarly, Dr. Sue Llewellyn says that dreams are impactful for daily behavior especially, if it is a highly emotional dream. Dr. Sofia Tzioridou, Robert Hoss, and Dr. Michael Schredl, also support the same idea.

Another similarity between all interviewees was their responses to the question regarding sleep stages and the effects it has on lucid dreaming. They all agreed on a consensus that REM sleep is the sleep stage with the most vivid lucid dreams because the brain is highly active. For example, Dr. Michael Schredl said, “Typically, lucid dreams occur during REM sleep (as the brain is very active, and dreaming is intense and story-like).”

One of the most important questions was regarding the techniques for becoming lucid and it was answered with very similar responses from all of the participants. For example, Dr. Valli, Dr. Tzioridou, and Hoss all mentioned MILD, Mnemonic Induction of Lucid Dreams, as a helpful lucid dreaming technique.

VIII. Limitations

Finally, if the researcher were to do this data collection again, they would choose to use the same method because the answers are very specific for the research, and the interviewer gets to ask as many questions as they wish for clarification. However, interviews might have a possible limitation of the interviewee not being able to answer a question which could be impactful for the data. So, the only change that the interviewer would make is to ensure that all interviewees have a similar background so that all questions can be asked well and assessed afterward.

Regarding the interviewees, it could be helpful to have people from different backgrounds, but it is crucial that they are all still well educated in lucid dreaming so that they can provide trustworthy and credible information. Additionally, it is important to discuss that every person has their own bias, and asking people from similar backgrounds and fields can cause them to have similar responses to the same questions. Lastly, the researcher only had access to free public academic journals.

IX. Discussion

The results of this data will be significant for future researchers because they answer many important questions with a direct answer. Also, another important question, “Do you think lucid dreaming could prevent nightmares?” was asked, and the responses were very hopeful. All interviewees believed that lucid dreaming could help patients who have nightmares. They believed that through training and learning about lucid dreaming, nightmares could begin to be eliminated for many patients, which is the next step for this research topic. However, Dr. Michael Schredl had an additional viewpoint that no other interviewees mentioned, he discussed lucid nightmares, which are the same things as nightmares just much more vivid. So, the future of this research is to find ways to prevent nightmares without causing more problems. But also, to understand how impactful lucid dreaming is to humans.

X. Conclusions

Thanks to the new data collected, future researchers can put the dots together and come up with a way to publicize how important lucid dreaming is. This new research introduces methods for becoming lucid and describes the benefits of each. It discusses the positive effects of lucid dreaming and how it can be used as a technique to treat nightmares. Lucid dreaming can help future generations come up with new ways to learn about humans and what causes their actions.

References

- Aspy, D. (2018, May 26). The easiest way to lucid dream, according to science.
https://docs.google.com/document/d/1V15-NWOOVvR_XQiYAWd-elbwbxmI465XiHET7vWzd7U/edit
- Baird, B., Dr. (2023, November 10). [Videoconference interview by the author].
- Baird B, Mota-Rolim SA, Dresler M. The cognitive neuroscience of lucid dreaming. *Neurosci Biobehav Rev.* 2019 May;100:305-323. doi: 10.1016/j.neubiorev.2019.03.008. Epub 2019 Mar 14. PMID: 30880167; PMCID: PMC6451677.
- Benjamin Baird, Giulio Tononi, Stephen LaBerge, Lucid dreaming occurs in activated rapid eye movement sleep, not a mixture of sleep and wakefulness, *Sleep*, Volume 45, Issue 4, April 2022, zsab294
- Gish, E. (2014, May). Lucid dreaming: A Wake-Initiated-Lucid-Dream (WILD) approach.
https://www.researchgate.net/publication/318946859_Lucid_dreaming_A_Wake-Initiated-Lucid-Dream_WILD_approach
- Holzinger B, Saletu B, Klösch G. Cognitions in Sleep: Lucid Dreaming as an Intervention for Nightmares in Patients With Posttraumatic Stress Disorder. *Front Psychol.* 2020 Aug 21;11:1826. doi: 10.3389/fpsyg.2020.01826. PMID: 32973600; PMCID: PMC7471655.
- LaBerge S, LaMarca K, Baird B. Pre-sleep treatment with galantamine stimulates lucid dreaming: A double-blind, placebo-controlled, crossover study. *PLoS One.* 2018 Aug 8;13(8):e0201246. doi: 10.1371/journal.pone.0201246. PMID: 30089135; PMCID: PMC6082533.
- Loo MR, Cheng SK. Dream Lucidity and the Attentional Network Task. *Front Psychol.* 2021 Jan 28;12:586808. doi: 10.3389/fpsyg.2021.586808. PMID: 33584468; PMCID: PMC7876060.
- Mallett R, Sowin L, Raider R, Konkoly KR, Paller KA. Benefits and concerns of seeking and experiencing lucid dreams: benefits are tied to successful induction and dream control. *Sleep Adv.* 2022 Sep 7;3(1):zpac027. doi: 10.1093/sleepadvances/zpac027. PMID: 37193400; PMCID: PMC10104404.
- Mayo Clinic. (2021, June 5). Nightmare Disorder - Symptoms and Causes - Mayo Clinic.
<https://www.mayoclinic.org/diseases-conditions/nightmare-disorder/symptoms-causes/syc-20353515>
- National Institute of Neurological Disorders and Stroke. (n.d.). Brain Basics: Understanding Sleep | National Institute of Neurological Disorder and Stroke.
<https://www.ninds.nih.gov/health-information/public-education/brain-basics/brain-basics-understanding-sleep#:~:text=Sleep%20is%20an%20important%20part,diabetes%2C%20depression%2C%20and%20obesity>
- Radtke, D. (2025, July 23). The Fascinating Neuroscience of Lucid Dreaming.
<https://www.brainfacts.org/thinking-sensing-and-behaving/sleep/2025/the-fascinating-neuroscience-of-lucid-dreaming-072325>
- Singh A, Gupta D. Can Acetylcholine make you dream? *Sleep Sci.* 2019 Jul-Sep;12(3):240-241. doi: 10.5935/1984-0063.20190096. PMID: 31890102; PMCID: PMC6932847.
- Sosnoski, K. (2023, July 24). The Mental Health Benefits and Downsides of Lucid Dreaming.
<https://www.healthline.com/health/lucid-dreaming-the-latest-on-its-mental-health-benefits-and-risks>

Sterpenich V, Perogamvros L, Tononi G, Schwartz S. Fear in dreams and in wakefulness: Evidence for day/night affective homeostasis. *Hum Brain Mapp.* 2020 Feb 15;41(3):840-850. doi: 10.1002/hbm.24843. Epub 2019 Oct 30. PMID: 31663236; PMCID: PMC7267911.

Stocks A, Carr M, Mallett R, Konkoly K, Hicks A, Crawford M, Schredl M, Bradshaw C. Dream lucidity is associated with positive waking mood. *Conscious Cogn.* 2020 Aug;83:102971. doi: 10.1016/j.concog.2020.102971. Epub 2020 Jun 11. PMID: 32535498.

Walker, M. (2017, October 24). Why Your Brain Needs to Dream | Greater Good.
https://greatergood.berkeley.edu/article/item/why_your_brain_needs_to_dream

Wamsley EJ. How the brain constructs dreams. *Elife.* 2020 Jun 8;9:e58874. doi: 10.7554/eLife.58874. PMID: 32508304; PMCID: PMC7279884.